

A.C. Polarographic Studies on the Nature of the Capacity Peaks observed with Organic Compounds at the Dropping Mercury Electrode. Part IV. Effect of Temperature and Frequency of the A. C. Ripple

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The effect of temperature and frequency of a.c. ripple on the peak potentials and magnitudes of tensammetric and reduction peaks, observed with organic compounds by a.c. polarography, have been studied. The fact that tensammetric peaks are reduced in magnitude and peak potentials shift to less negative values, whereas reduction peaks are either enhanced or remain constant in magnitude and peak potentials are independent, with rise in temperature, has been utilised in elucidating the nature of the a.c. peaks observed with organic compounds at the d.m.e. The effect of frequency of a.c. ripple on the magnitudes of these peaks shows that tensammetric rate processes are faster than the rates corresponding to the reduction of organic compounds.

Breyer and Bauer¹ studied the effect of change of temperature on the a.c. polarographic peaks of hydroquinone and chloroanilic acid and found that the sensitivity increased at lower temperatures. Breyer and Hacobian² also showed that the wave heights and E_p values of the organic compounds decreased with increasing temperature. Gupta³ found that the magnitude of the desorption peaks decreased with increase in frequency of the pulsating field.

The present investigation deals with further detailed studies of the effect of temperature and frequency of the a.c. ripple on the peak potentials and magnitudes of the a.c. peaks, observed with a number of organic compounds, known to provide tensammetric as well as reduction peaks, with a view to ascertaining the utility of these effects in distinguishing their nature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromothymol blue was of B.D.H. indicator quality. Corfak and cetylpyridinium bromide were commercial detergents. Organic solid compounds used were either B.D.H. or Merck's quality and were recrystallised before use. Organic liquid substances were also pure samples of either Merck or B.D.H. and were redistilled in all-glass fractionating column and middle one thirds of the distillates were used for experiments. Other inorganic

1. *Austral. J. Sci.*, 1955, **8**, 467, 472.
2. *Ibid.*, 1952, **5**, 500.
3. (a) *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1954, **39A**, 283.
(b) *Kolloid Z.*, 1958, **160**, 30.
(c) *Proc. Natl. Inst. Sci., India*, 1958, **24A**, 377.

chemicals used were AnalaR quality of B.D.H. Mercury used for dropping electrode was purified as mentioned earlier⁴.

The experimental set-up and the technique of measurement were same as described before⁴. Negative d.c. potentials were applied to the d.m.e. with respect to the S.C.E. and all the experiments were done at pH 10.4. The d.m.e. was cathodic throughout the measurements and its constants were $m = 4.564$ mg./sec. and $t = 1.8$ sec./drop in 0.1M.KCl, open circuit.

The effect of temperature and frequency of the a.c. ripple on the behaviour of organic compounds was studied by using a thermostat (Townsend & Mercer Ltd., England) and a frequency oscillator (Philips, No. GM 2308) respectively.

DISCUSSION

Effect of Temperature on Tensammetric Peaks

Table I records the effect of temperature on the peak potentials and the magnitude of the tensammetric peaks observed with a number of organic compounds, known to provide tensammetric peaks. In general, it can be seen that the magnitude of the peak diminishes and the peak potential shifts to a less negative value with rise in temperature. Benzaldehyde, in which the magnitude remains constant and the peak potential shifts to a more negative value with rise in temperature, as well as ionic surfactants such as cerfak, cetylpyridinium bromide and bromothymol blue, which provide increased magnitudes with rise in temperature, shows discrepancy for the above behaviour. This discrepancy may be due to chemical interaction between benzaldehyde and sodium hydroxide at alkaline pH in the case of benzaldehyde and due to specific charge interaction between the charged ions and the double layer in the case of ionic surfactants. The decrease in the magnitudes of the tensammetric peaks and the shift of the peak potentials to less negative values with increase in temperature are due to the decrease in the extent of adsorption of the surface-active molecule at higher temperatures.

Effect of Temperature on the Reduction Peaks of Organic Compounds

Table II shows the effect of temperature on the magnitudes of the a.c. peaks and their peak potentials, observed with a number of organic compounds known to exhibit reduction peaks. In general, it can be seen that either the magnitude of the peak increases or practically remains constant with increase in temperature. Further, the peak potential is independent of temperature. This increase in the magnitude of the reduction peak is due to the increased rate of electrode process when the temperature is raised. These results are supported by the observations of Breyer and Bauer¹ in which they showed that with concentrations $\geq 3 \times 10^{-4}$ M of the substance, the magnitude of the peak increases with rise in temperature, whereas with concentrations less than this, the magnitude diminishes with increase in temperature, thus showing that the effect of temperature on the height of the wave varies with the concentration of the organic substance. This effect observed by them can be explained as follows.

4. This Journal, 1964, 41, 663.

According to Breyer³ the a.c. peaks due to the reduction of organic compounds are "composite" in nature. At lower concentrations of the substance, the tensammetric part of the composite peak predominates over the reduction part and hence the magnitude of the peak decreases with increase in temperature. At higher concentrations, the reduction part predominates over the tensammetric part and thus the magnitude increases with rise in temperature. This is further supported by the fact that the concentration *vs.* peak height curve is linear at lower concentrations of the substance, whereas it is nonlinear at higher concentrations. It is also observed that the peak height obtained in the reduction of inorganic cations increases much more than that due to the reduction of organic compounds for the same rise in temperature and the peak potential remains constant. This observation further supports the "composite" nature of the peaks obtained in the reduction of organic compounds.

TABLE I
50 c/s a.c. ripple of ± 40 mV (r.m.s.). pH=10.4.

Substance.	Conc.	*	Temperature.					
			10°.	20°.	30°.	40°.	50°.	60°.
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	1.0%	A	-1.25	-1.22	-1.17	-1.16	-1.15	-1.14
		B	184	169	156	144	120	104
<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.0%	A	-1.22	-1.21	-1.21	-1.20	-1.195	-1.19
		B	159	151	145	138	126	113
Resorcinol	1.0%	A	-1.07	-1.05	-1.04	-1.03	-1.025	-1.02
		B	70	65	62	59	50	47
Phloroglucinol	1.0%	A	-1.06	-1.05	-1.02	-0.95	-0.84	-0.8
		B	228	213	194	175	158	111
Benzoic acid	0.01M	A	-1.06	-1.06	-1.04	-1.02	-0.99	-0.98
		B	60	53	38	24	21	8
Pyridine	1.0%	A	-1.39	-1.39	-1.36	-1.34	-1.31	-1.27
		B	215	214	210	196	130	100
Anisole	Satd.	A	-1.32	-1.31	-1.30	-1.29	-1.28	-1.27
		B	202	194	187	168	156	144
Benzene	Satd.	A	-0.94	-0.93	-0.90	-0.88	-0.87	..
		B	163	136	86	47	43	..
Toluene	Satd.	A	-1.01	-0.98	-0.97	-0.96	-0.94	-0.93
		B	148	130	121	95	82	69
Benzaldehyde	$2 \times 10^{-3}M$	A	-1.47	-1.49	-1.50	-1.50	-1.51	-1.51
		B	89	88	88	90	89	89
Cerfak	0.1%	A	-1.35	-1.34	-1.33	-1.32	-1.29	-1.29
		B	126	143	157	157	157	157
Cetylpyridinium bromide	0.1%	A	..	-1.36	-1.35	-1.34	-1.31	-1.29
		B	..	35	45	47	53	61
Bromothymol blue	0.004%	A	-0.98	-0.98	-0.97	-0.97	-0.97	-0.65
		B	53	66	73	83	87	87

*A denotes peak potential in volts and B, % increase in a.c. in μA .

Effect of Frequency of the A.C. Ripple

Fig. 1 represents the typical curves showing the plot of frequency against log of peak height of tensammetric peak (curve 1) and the reduction peak (curve 2) observed with

saturated solution of benzene and $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ *m*-nitrobenzoic acid respectively. The magnitudes of the tensammetric and reduction peaks of organic compounds are found generally to diminish progressively with increase in frequency of the a.c. ripple, whereas the peak potentials for both types of the peaks remain constant.

TABLE II
Conditions same as in Table I.

Substance.	Conc.	*	Temperature.					
			10°	20°	30°	40°	50°	60°
<i>p</i> -Nitroaniline	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	A	-0.86	-0.86	-0.86	-0.86	-0.86	-0.86
		B	77	117	143	160	166	171
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenol	$2 \times$..	A	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8
		B	32	34	35	38	42	47
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenol	$4 \times$..	A	-0.82	-0.82	-0.82	-0.82	-0.82	-0.82
		B	115	120	125	132	140	151
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	$4 \times$..	A	..	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98	-0.98
		B	..	131	153	160	182	196
Nitrobenzene	$2 \times$..	A	-0.81	-0.81	-0.81	-0.81	-0.81	-0.81
		B	46	47	49	50	54	57
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	$4 \times$..	A	..	..	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8	-0.8
		B	..	..	142	142	145	145
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	$4 \times$..	A	..	..	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71
		B	..	..	142	143	142	142
3, 5-Dinitrobenzoic acid	$4 \times$..	A	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71	-0.71
		B	153	171	173	175	176	180
Benzaldehyde (pH 3.8)	$1 \times 10^{-3} M$	A	..	..	-1.18	-1.19	-1.20	-1.20
		B	..	..	53	53	62	67

*Same as in Table I.

FIG. 1

1 - Satd. benzene
2 - $4 \times 10^{-4} M$ *m*-nitrobenzoic acid.

Table III records the values of frequency required to diminish the magnitude of the tensammetric and reduction peaks to half their initial values at 50 cycles. It can be seen that higher frequency is required to diminish the magnitude of the tensammetric peak to half its value than that for reduction peak under similar conditions. This shows that the rate of the electrode process corresponding to the tensammetric peaks is faster than the rate of the process corresponding to the reduction of organic compounds at the d.m.e.

NATURE OF CAPACITY PEAKS OBSERVED WITH ORGANIC COMPOUNDS AT D.M.E: 57

TABLE III

Conditions same as in Table I.

Substances.	Conc. (%)	Magnitude of peak. (% a.c.)	Frequency required to reduce the magnitude to half its value (cycles).
Tensammetric peaks.			
<i>n</i> -Amyl alcohol	1.0	174	250
Benzene	Satd.	174	220
<i>o</i> -Cresol	1.0	171	250
Cerlak	0.1	162	155
Bromothymol blue	0.01	229	150
Reduction peaks.			
Nitrobenzene	$4 \times 10^{-4} M$	146	105
<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	"	212	100
<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	"	152	110
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol	"	174	110

It may therefore be concluded that the effect of temperature on the peak potential and the magnitude of the capacity peaks observed with organic compounds can be utilised for elucidating the nature of the peaks at the d.m.e. The tensammetric rate processes are faster than the rates of the reduction processes of organic compounds under similar conditions.

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